

Advancements in Cancer Gene Therapy: Exploring Biological Mechanisms and Innovative Treatment Strategies

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Abstract

In recent years, cancer has emerged as one of the most significant health issues and is the second leading cause of death after heart disease. Cancer is characterized by the uncontrolled proliferation of cells and the formation of tumors in the human body. With the advent of recent bioinformatics and genetic technologies, it has become increasingly possible to identify, diagnose, and determine potential cancer treatments. Several in vitro and in vivo approaches to cancer treatment have been studied, including naked nucleic acid therapy, microRNA targeting, oncolytic virus therapy, telomerase targeting, cell-mediated gene therapy, and CRISPR/Cas9-based therapy. In this article, we first examine the biology and occurrence of cancer, highlight various viral and non-viral gene delivery systems for gene therapy, and then discuss current and emerging strategies for cancer gene therapy.

Keywords: Gene therapy, Gene, Cancer, Proliferation, Immunity.

1. Introduction

Cancer, the second leading cause of death after heart disease, is caused by the uncontrolled proliferation of cells and the formation of tumors in the human body [1]. The disease arises from genetic lesions in genes encoding cell cycle proteins or as a result of somatic mutations in upstream cell signaling pathways. Despite the increasing availability of conventional cancer treatment options, millions of patients die from cancer each year [2]. Due to cancer cell metastasis, recurrence, heterogeneity, and resistance to chemotherapy and radiotherapy, many traditional treatment methods are ineffective against various malignant tumors [3].

The ability of cancer cells to evade the immune response has also been reported as a significant reason for treatment failure. Conventional cancer treatment methods often fail to provide satisfactory results. Among all treatment methods, chemotherapy is the most widely used option for many cancer treatments. However, literature indicates that conventional chemotherapeutic agents have limitations, including nonspecific distribution, poor

bioavailability, rapid blood clearance, and relatively poor solubility in body fluids [4,5].

The ultimate goal of any cancer therapeutic agent is to selectively kill tumor cells while preventing damage to surrounding healthy cells and tissues, a goal that has yet to be fully achieved. Currently, gene therapy offers suitable treatment options for many genetic-related diseases, including cancer, and provides the theoretical advantage of achieving therapeutic goals with a single treatment. In this review, we provide up-to-date information on the current status of gene delivery strategies as treatment options for various cancers and the potential of each for future clinical trials as promising cancer treatments.

2. Cancer Biology

Cancer is defined as irregular and uncontrolled cell division and growth. It can occur in any cell type in the human body and aggressively invades different areas, with metastasis and invasion being associated with the malignant behavior of many cancer cells. Transformed cells exhibit altered metabolism to support tumor initiation and progression [6,7,8].

Epidemiological studies have consistently shown a significant increase in cancer rates associated with exposure to certain factors, consumption of specific foods and beverages, infection with certain microbes, and deficiencies in certain metals or vitamins. It has recently been estimated that microorganisms are responsible for approximately 20% of all cancer types worldwide [9].

Various carcinogenic viruses, such as human papillomavirus, hepatitis B and C viruses, and Epstein-Barr virus, as well as the oncogenic bacterium *Helicobacter pylori* and several carcinogenic parasites, have been investigated. Recent advances in bioinformatics and metagenomic technologies have provided new insights into the role of microorganisms and microbial ecology in the progression of various cancers [10].

Studies have examined the role of normal intestinal flora in the pathogenesis of colorectal cancer, revealing that many intestinal microbiomes are significantly increased in patients with this type of cancer. Other studies have investigated the role of human papillomavirus in head and neck squamous cell cancer, demonstrating its prevalence. Additionally, research has emphasized the importance of microbe-host interactions in different parts of the human body and their role in cancer prevention [11,12].

Poor diet and unhealthy lifestyle choices are associated with more than 80,000 cancer cases annually [13]. Factors such as body weight, physical activity, vitamin and mineral intake, and even lack of sleep are linked to increased rates of various cancers [14]. A healthy immune system can regularly fight and destroy cancerous or precancerous cells; however, a weakened immune system due to poor diet or microbial infection increases the risk of developing cancer [15].

Cancer caused by inherited defective genes is estimated by geneticists to account for 3-10% of all diagnosed cases [16]. Different cancer-related gene errors increase the risk of developing various types of cancer, making family history crucial in cancer diagnosis. Human tissues contain a family of small membrane-bound water transport proteins known as aquaporins. Numerous studies have shown that aquaporins are closely related to the cellular biological function of more than 20 types of human cancer [17]. The expression of aquaporins correlates positively with many tumor characteristics, including tumor types, grades, growth and proliferation, metastasis, angiogenesis, and even tumor-related edema [18,19]. However, somatic mutations alone are not sufficient to induce cancer or tumorigenesis.

Treatment Options for Cancer Patients

In recent years, advancements and the variety of available treatment options have significantly increased the number of cancer survivors. The first generation of effective therapeutic agents used to treat cancer consisted of cytotoxics, which form the main therapeutic regimens. Several factors influence cancer treatment options, including the type and stage of cancer, general health, and the availability of treatment approaches. Surgery and chemotherapy are the most common methods successfully used to treat millions of patients. However, complications may arise

depending on the patient's health status, and these methods may not be suitable for more advanced cancer cases.

Radiation therapy is another treatment option that has been employed for many cancer types, utilizing high-energy beams such as protons, electrical energy, or X-rays to target and destroy cancer cells. Nanoparticles have been utilized as carriers for anticancer drugs, showing promising results [20].

Bone marrow or stem cell transplantation from a matched sibling or unrelated donor is becoming a desirable treatment option for certain cancers, such as leukemia and lymphoma [21]. Cryoablation has been proposed as an alternative to surgery for treating specific types of cancer in selected patients at early stages. Cryoablation is considered an emerging treatment option for various malignant and benign diseases and continues to be developed. Cancer immunotherapy involves treating cancer cells by modulating the immune system.

3. Gene Therapy

The introduction of new treatment technologies for chronic diseases such as cancer has been crucial. The dramatic advancements in recent years stem from the desire to overcome the disadvantages and challenges associated with conventional treatment options. Gene therapy has been bolstered by advances in bioinformatics and the development of various high-throughput genomic methods capable of identifying specific mutations for targeted gene delivery. Studies have reported four main strategies in gene therapy: replacing the desired gene, modifying it, increasing the gene, and blocking the defective gene. Over 2,200 gene therapy-based clinical trials have been conducted worldwide [22], with approximately 60% related to cancer gene therapy, indicating the effectiveness of gene therapy in cancer treatment beyond hereditary diseases. Various gene therapy strategies have been developed for cancer treatment, including anti-angiogenic gene therapy, immunomodulatory gene therapy, suicide gene therapy, siRNA therapy, oncolytic gene therapy, and pro-apoptotic gene therapy. Gene therapy has shown promising potential as a treatment option for cancer and many other diseases [23].

Gene Delivery Approaches

Safe and efficient gene delivery is fundamental to successful gene therapy. Several characteristics have been proposed for ideal gene delivery systems, including broad capacity for gene insertion, high gene transfer rates, tumor cell type-specific selectivity, stable gene expression, availability, and safety. Gene transfer systems are classified into two main groups: viral and non-viral gene therapy vectors.

Virus-Based Gene Transfer System

Virus-based gene delivery systems were the first vectors studied and used, and they currently comprise the most practical gene delivery systems. Viral vectors can transfer loaded genetic material to target host cells following the natural mechanisms of viral infection and replication. Genetic modifications are necessary to enhance the efficacy, safety, and uptake of viral vectors [24].

Several viral vectors have been used in gene transfer, including adeno-associated virus, lentivirus, adenovirus, retrovirus, and herpes simplex virus. Studies have demonstrated that viral vectors have higher transduction efficiency than non-viral delivery systems, with long-term gene expression. Research using engineered herpes simplex virus vectors has shown significant long-term expression, indicating their suitability for diseases requiring prolonged transgene expression. However, viral vectors have certain weaknesses and limitations, including immunogenicity, toxicity, mutagenicity, high costs, and limited carrying capacity in certain viruses [25].

Non-Viral Based Gene Transfer System

Recent decades have seen significant development in various non-viral gene delivery systems, extensively tested for safety and delivery capacity, driven by the desire to overcome the limitations associated with viral vectors. Non-viral gene transfer systems are classified into three main groups: physical-mediated methods, chemical vectors, and biological methods. Non-viral biological vectors generally refer to bacteria and certain mammalian cells. Various bacteria, including attenuated strains of Bifidobacteria, Salmonella, Shigella, Clostridia, Yersinia, Listeria, and non-pathogenic Escherichia coli, have been used as gene vectors. Mesenchymal stem cells and blood cells are the most commonly used mammalian cells for gene therapy. Non-viral vectors offer several advantages over viral ones, including relative immunity to many non-viral variants, and the ability to transfer larger-sized genes, which cannot be achieved using viral vectors.

Gene Therapy for Cancer Treatment

The capacity of various gene therapy methods for treating cancers is increasingly recognized, as evidenced by the growing number of clinical trials each year [26]. Different types of cancer tumors are being targeted using multiple strategies, including plasmid/DNA therapy, microRNA targeting, oncolytic viral therapy, therapies targeting telomerase, tumor suppressor gene delivery, and enzyme-directed drug therapy. Gene targeting is among the most commonly used therapeutic approaches, with numerous studies conducted in these areas.

Treatment Based on Targeted MicroRNAs

MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are a family of small functional non-coding endogenous RNAs, approximately 18–22 nucleotides in length, that play important roles in gene expression and regulation by targeting several molecules. Reports indicate that miRNAs may significantly inhibit or promote many cancer-related genes, affecting several cell signaling pathways essential for tumor growth, development, and progression. The expression of miRNAs has been shown to be significantly altered in various cancer cell lines and tumor tissues, influencing most cellular biological processes, including cell viability, proliferation, motility, survival, and differentiation [27].

Following apoptotic cell death and necrosis, miRNAs are released into the bloodstream, saliva, or other tissues, depending on the cell type [28], and are transported by various extracellular

vesicles in the blood, where they combine with many protein complexes. The use of messenger RNA (mRNA) synthesis in cancer treatment is emerging as a promising therapeutic alternative that induces transient protein expression. Alternative splicing of pre-mRNA is a common mechanism for generating mRNA isoforms from a limited set of genes.

Therapies Targeting Telomerase

Telomerase is a type of ribonucleoprotein that is enzymatically active in 80-90% of malignant tumors [29]. In addition to contributing to the immortality of cancer cells, this protein maintains genes at the terminal structures of human chromosomes [30]. The critical role of telomerase in cancer mechanisms has attracted significant scientific interest as a promising therapeutic target. Many researchers have proposed targeting telomerase to prevent the limitless replicative potential of cancer cells, making it an attractive strategy for treating various cancers [31]. Studies have reported the design of 64 new compounds as telomerase inhibitors, evaluating their activity against different cancer cell lines. Certain compounds exhibited excellent telomerase inhibitory activity and demonstrated good efficacy against cancer cells [32].

Oncolytic Virus Therapy

Many viruses can specifically target certain types of cancer cells, replicate within them, and lead to their lysis, effectively killing the cancer cells [33]. Oncolytic viruses are natural or genetically modified viral species that selectively infect and kill cancer cells. This inherent or conferred feature has generated considerable interest in using oncolytic viruses as highly targeted agents that mediate anti-cancer effects. Evidence suggests that the therapeutic potential of oncolytic virus therapy is not solely due to cell damage but also relies on inducing an innate immune response against altered cells. Notably, extraordinary anticancer effects are observed when oncolytic viruses are engineered to express immune-stimulating molecules or are administered alongside them.

Cell-Mediated Gene Therapy

Cell-mediated gene therapy is one of the newest approaches used in cancer treatment. Various terms, including cell therapy and cytotherapy, refer to using living cells to restore the biological activities of damaged organs or tissues [34]. Studies have reported that therapeutic cells taken from specific patients can replace, repair, or enhance the function, shape, and morphology of damaged cells, tissues, or organs, offering hope to cancer patients with incurable tumors.

CRISPR-Cas9 Method

The CRISPR-Cas9 method is one of the newest techniques with great potential for cancer gene therapy. This technique utilizes the Cas9 protein system to achieve efficient and accurate gene editing, leading to permanent changes in only the desired genes and resulting in effective cancer treatment. CRISPR-Cas9-mediated genome editing has been reported to be more flexible, feasible, and efficient, as the Cas9 protein binds to the desired site and cleaves the target DNA sequences, causing double-strand

breaks located within three nucleotides before the known sequence. CRISPR-Cas9 has been widely tested in recent years as a promising cancer therapy, pursuing various strategies such as genome editing of cancer cells, immunotherapy, anticancer drug delivery, stroma-targeted therapies, and combating cancer-causing viruses.

4. Conclusion

Gene therapy is an advanced technology that offers tremendous therapeutic potential for the treatment of various tumors. As evidenced by published research and clinical trials, new strategies are continually being developed. Cancer gene therapy, utilizing the techniques discussed, promises to usher in a new era for tumor treatment and improve the quality of life for patients, particularly

those with advanced tumors. Targeting genes to enhance the production of immune cytokines and bolster the anti-cancer immune response may be a preferred approach for many researchers. However, this approach is limited in its general applicability, necessitating that current and future generations of gene therapy focus on highly specific gene editing strategies to ensure long-term safety. Despite significant advances in gene delivery systems and a solid understanding of cancer genetics, challenges remain in developing mechanisms capable of correcting the activation of oncogenes without affecting normal genes. Future research in cancer gene therapy should foster collaboration among engineers, medical professionals, physicists, chemists, and biologists to better understand the specifics of gene editing strategies and their potential long-term effects.

References

1. Paules, C. I., Marston, H. D., & Fauci, A. S. (2020). Coronavirus infections—more than just the common cold. *Jama*, 323(8), 707-708.
2. Galanakis, C. M. (2020). The food systems in the era of the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic crisis. *Foods*, 9(4), 523.
3. Keil, S. D., Bowen, R., & Marschner, S. (2016). Inactivation of Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) in plasma products using a riboflavin-based and ultraviolet light-based photochemical treatment. *Transfusion*, 56(12), 2948-2952.
4. Das, U. N. (2020). Can bioactive lipids inactivate coronavirus (COVID-19)? *Archives of medical research*, 51(3), 282-286.
5. Hemilä, H., & Chalker, E. (2013). Vitamin C for preventing and treating the common cold. *Cochrane database of systematic reviews*, (1).
6. Abdelkebir, R., Alcántara, C., Falcó, I., Sánchez, G., Garcia-Perez, J. V., Neffati, M., ... & Collado, M. C. (2019). Effect of ultrasound technology combined with binary mixtures of ethanol and water on antibacterial and antiviral activities of *Erodium glaucophyllum* extracts. *Innovative food science & emerging technologies*, 52, 189-196.
7. Gasmi, A., Noor, S., Tippairote, T., Dadar, M., Menzel, A., & Bjørklund, G. (2020). Individual risk management strategy and potential therapeutic options for the COVID-19 pandemic. *Clinical immunology*, 215, 108409.
8. Chang, H. C., Bayeva, M., Taiwo, B., Palella Jr, F. J., Hope, T. J., & Ardehali, H. (2015). High cellular iron levels are associated with increased HIV infection and replication. *AIDS research and human retroviruses*, 31(3), 305-312.
9. Chin, K. Y., & Ima-Nirwana, S. (2018). The role of vitamin E in preventing and treating osteoarthritis—a review of the current evidence. *Frontiers in pharmacology*, 9, 946.
10. Chaichian, S., Moazzami, B., Sadoughi, F., Haddad Kashani, H., Zaroudi, M., & Asemi, Z. (2020). Functional activities of beta-glucans in the prevention or treatment of cervical cancer. *Journal of Ovarian Research*, 13, 1-12.
11. Luo, H., Tang, Q. L., Shang, Y. X., Liang, S. B., Yang, M., Robinson, N., & Liu, J. P. (2020). Can Chinese medicine be used for prevention of corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19)? A review of historical classics, research evidence and current prevention programs. *Chinese journal of integrative medicine*, 26(4), 243-250.
12. Kwon, P. S., Oh, H., Kwon, S. J., Jin, W., Zhang, F., Fraser, K., ... & Dordick, J. S. (2020). Sulfated polysaccharides effectively inhibit SARS-CoV-2 in vitro. *Cell discovery*, 6(1), 50.
13. Singh, R. S., Walia, A. K., & Kennedy, J. F. (2020). Mushroom lectins in biomedical research and development. *International journal of biological macromolecules*, 151, 1340-1350.
14. Mullin, G. E. (2011). Vitamin A and immunity. *Nutrition in Clinical Practice*, 26(4).
15. Ling, C. Q. (2020). Traditional Chinese medicine is a resource for drug discovery against 2019 novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2). *Journal of integrative medicine*, 18(2), 87.
16. Sarohan, A. R. (2020). COVID-19: endogenous retinoic acid theory and retinoic acid depletion syndrome. *Medical hypotheses*, 144, 110250.
17. Semba, R. D., Ndugwa, C., Perry, R. T., Clark, T. D., Jackson, J. B., Melikian, G., ... & Mmiro, F. (2005). Effect of periodic vitamin A supplementation on mortality and morbidity of human immunodeficiency virus-infected children in Uganda: a controlled clinical trial. *Nutrition*, 21(1), 25-31.
18. Jayawardena, R., Sooriyaarachchi, P., Chourdakis, M., Jeewandara, C., & Ranasinghe, P. (2020). Enhancing immunity in viral infections, with special emphasis on COVID-19: A review. *Diabetes & Metabolic Syndrome: Clinical Research & Reviews*, 14(4), 367-382.
19. Vyas, N., Kurian, S. J., Bagchi, D., Manu, M. K., Saravu, K., Unnikrishnan, M. K., ... & Miraj, S. S. (2021). Vitamin D in prevention and treatment of COVID-19: current perspective and future prospects. *Journal of the American College of Nutrition*, 40(7), 632-645.
20. Gasmi, A., Noor, S., Tippairote, T., Dadar, M., Menzel, A., & Bjørklund, G. (2020). Individual risk management strategy and potential therapeutic options for the COVID-19 pandemic. *Clinical immunology*, 215, 108409.

21. Colunga Biancatelli, R. M. L., Berrill, M., & Marik, P. E. (2020). The antiviral properties of vitamin C. *Expert review of anti-infective therapy*, 18(2), 99-101.
22. Gombart, A. F., Pierre, A., & Maggini, S. (2020). A review of micronutrients and the immune system—working in harmony to reduce the risk of infection. *Nutrients*, 12(1), 236.
23. Alpert, P. T. (2017). The role of vitamins and minerals on the immune system. *Home Health Care Management & Practice*, 29(3), 199-202.
24. Gupta, S., Read, S. A., Shackel, N. A., Hebbard, L., George, J., & Ahlenstiel, G. (2019). The role of micronutrients in the infection and subsequent response to hepatitis C virus. *Cells*, 8(6), 603.
25. Santos, D. I., Saraiva, J. M. A., Vicente, A. A., & Moldão-Martins, M. (2019). Methods for determining bioavailability and bioaccessibility of bioactive compounds and nutrients. In *Innovative thermal and non-thermal processing, bioaccessibility and bioavailability of nutrients and bioactive compounds* (pp. 23-54). Woodhead Publishing.